

Abstracts

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diseases of onion. The fungicides namely mancozeb @ 0.25%, propiconazole @ 0.1%, copper oxychloride @ 0.25%, tricyclazole @ 0.1% and hexaconazole @ 0.1% were tested alone and in combination with insecticides namely methomyl @ 0.8g/L, carbosulfan @ 2ml/L and profenofos @ 1ml/L in the present study. The percent disease intensity and incidence of foliar disease were recorded before each spray at fortnightly intervals on randomly selected ten plants of onion following the 0-5 rating scale.

The pooled data of two years revealed that the lowest incidence (20.0%) and intensity (3.75%) of stemphylium blight disease as well as highest gross yield (156.51q/ha) of onion bulbs were recorded in sequential foliar spray of fungicides in combination with insecticides in T3 (mancozeb @ 0.25%+methomyl @ 0.8g/L, propiconazole @ 0.1%+carbosulfan @ 2ml/L, copper oxychloride @ 0.25%+profenofos @ 1ml/L), however, highest marketable yield (126.04q/ha) was recorded in T4 (mancozeb @ 0.25%+methomyl @ 0.8g/L, tricyclazole @ 0.1%+carbosulfan @ 2ml/L, hexaconazole @ 0.1%+profenofos @ 1ml/L). The data further revealed that purple blotch disease did not appear in T3 (mancozeb @0.25%+methomyl @0.8g/L, propiconazole @0.1%+carbosulfan @2ml/L, copper oxychloride @0.25%+profenofos @ 1ml/L) and T4 (mancozeb @ 0.25%+methomyl @ 0.8g/L, tricyclazole @0.1%+carbosulfan @2ml/L, hexaconazole @0.1%+profenofos @1ml/L) on onion crop during the cropping period.

The highest stemphylium blight incidence (37.50%) with intensity (6.45%) and purple blotch incidence (22.50%) with intensity (1.30%) were recorded on onion crop in untreated check. The lowest gross yield (124.08q/ha) and marketable yield (83.17q/ha) were recorded in untreated check. The study thus, revealed that combined sprays of fungicides and insecticides effectively control the stemphylium blight and purple blotch diseases as well as increase yield of onion bulbs during *khariif* season in Nashik area of Maharashtra.

TS4: P-3

Effect of abiotic factors on the incidence of hadda beetle (*Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata*) on muskmelon and watermelon in arid region of Rajasthan

S M Haldhar, B R Choudhary, R Bhargava and S K Sharma*

Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Bikaner-334006 (Rajasthan)

*Email: haldhar80@gmail.com

The muskmelon and watermelon are gaining popularity among the farmers of arid and semi- arid areas for commercial cultivation. However, the quality of fruits and productivity is not obtained up to the standard. One of the reasons is infestation of insect pests on the vegetative as well as developing fruits, which ultimately leads to significant yield loss and quality attributes of the fruits. Looking in to the severity of insect pest infestation, we have conducted study throughout the year at Experimental Farm, Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Bikaner during 2011-12. The damaging effect of hadda beetle, *Henosepilachna vigintioctopunctata* was recorded on muskmelon and watermelon from March to June. The damaging intensity of this beetle was recorded between 20 to 29 percent leaves damage. The minimum population (0.27 in muskmelon & 0.47 in watermelon per plant) of beetle was recorded in the month of March (first fortnight). The mean population of beetle (2.88 per plant in muskmelon and 2.39 per plant in watermelon) were recorded. Maximum population of hadda beetle (6.67 & 5.47 per plant in muskmelon & watermelon, respectively) was recorded in the month of June (first fortnight). The relationship between hadda beetle population in muskmelon (0.83) and watermelon (0.79) with maximum temperature was positively correlated whereas, the maximum relative humidity was (-0.35 & -0.39) negatively correlated. The rainfall was also positively correlated (0.58 & 0.66) with beetle population of muskmelon and watermelon in arid region. It is concluded that the beetle population gradually increased and reached to its peak, when the temperature increased and humidity decreased.